

Appraisal of Legislative Process and Drafting in Nigeria

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Abstract

Legislative drafting is a process by which policies and proposals are put in a legislative language called Bill which consequently becomes the Act of Parliament if it passes through all the stages of law making. The impact that a law has on societal development depends on the brilliance of the bill drafting as well as the process of making the bill to be law. A law that is a product of a poorly drafted Bill perhaps as a result of drafting it in a hurry, inadequate consultation with stakeholders, and insufficient examination by the appropriate law department, makes life difficult not only for the people but also for the government. In view of the importance of legislative drafting to socio-economic and political life of a people, this article will discuss the required skills for standard legislative drafting as well as the legislative process and procedures to be followed by the draftsman and make appropriate suggestions for excellent legislative drafting.

Keywords: Legislation, Draftsman, Bill, Skills, Process, drafting

INTRODUCTION

Legislative drafting is a critical aspect of law-making in any organized society. In our constitutional democracy wherein the organic law is the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (As amended). Legislative drafting is a veritable instrument for distilling and ventilating policies and ideas of government both at the Federal and State

1. Prof. Epiphany Azinge; Fundamentals of Legislative Drafting. Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies 2012

levels. It is, nevertheless, useful and often necessary for reaching the goals of social policy. In all Organised societies, certain basic structures and rules are needed. The State strives to influence the society and control the behaviour of individuals through other direct and indirect means.

It is a means of communicating a given information in a permanent form. Simplicity, it is the art of drafting legislations. The legislative process is referred to as the process by which a statute is made i.e 1st, 2nd, and 3rd reading and assent whereas legislative drafting is an act which is executed by those who are specially trained in the art of legislative drafting.

SKILLS FOR STANDARD LEGISLATIVE DRAFTING

- a. A drafter must have a good command of English Language.
- b. Must ensure clarity without ambiguity while drafting.
- c. Make use of sections and subsections. It is advisable that a section should contain one main idea which should be self-explanatory, short, lucid and devoid of ambiguity. Where the composition of the section turns out to be long out to be a long one, the proper thing for a draftsman to do is to break the section into sub-sections.
- d. The use of punctuations such as comma, full stop, colon, inverted commas, quotation marks, etc. must be taken into consideration in drafting an enactment in accordance with section 3(1) of the Interpretation Act.
- e. Make use of paragraphs especially where a section or sub-section of a statute becomes unreasonably long. The essence is to help in the readability of the sentence and it also creates precision in the understanding of the legislative intent. A paragraph may be divided into sub-paragraphs particularly where the paragraph in the sentence becomes too long.
- f. Make use of schedules to supply supplementary details. Schedules exhibit in detail matters or information mentioned or referred to in the principal body of the Bill or legislation. Details of information, statistics, figures, tables and other special or technical matters highlighted or referred to in the body of an enactment are contained in the Schedule.
- g. Take note of existing laws because there is no Bill that is not related remotely or otherwise to any existing law. This helps the draftsman to avoid repetitive legislation.
- h. The draftsman must have a sound understanding of policy issues, the shape, contents and policy-related issues concerning the proposed legislation because by

2. Prof. Matti Niemivuo: "Legislative Drafting Process. Main Issues And Some Examples"; European Commission For Democracy Through Law (Venice Commission)

3. Prof. O.B. Akinola: Principles of Law in Practice (Professional Ethics & skills)

4. *ibid*

5. Cap 1 LFN 2004

virtue of the position of the draftsman, he is presumed and in fact, expected to be familiar with the law on a wide range of issues of legislative proposal in a wider and more balanced perspective than the law makers.

- I. The legislation must be drafted in a way that it will be practicable as the law does not compel the doing of the impossible.

QUALITIES OF LEGISLATIVE DRAFTSMAN

This draftsman is an architect of social structures, an expert in the design of frameworks of collaboration for all kinds of purposes, a specialist in the high art of speaking to the future, knowing when and how to try and bind it and when not to try at all. The following qualities must be demonstrated by a good legislative draftsman. They are:

- i. Intellectual intelligence and stamina
- ii. Ability to analyze an issue or problem in details
- iii. Knowledge of other laws especially the constitution so that the proposed law or Bill will be in contradiction to it owing to the inconsistency rule in section 1(3) of the 1999 Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria.

VARIOUS STAGES OF DRAFTING

Receiving and understanding the draft

The process of drafting legislations may be said to begin with the receipt of drafting instructions and end with completion of an agreed draft. At this stage, the draftsman requests for key information from the instructing authority such as the policy behind the Bill. Therefore, the draftsman should direct his mind to one of two things or indeed both:

- a. He can make clear to those instructing him of drafting instructions which is most helpful to him. This can be done on a case by case basis and, for example, he can get in touch with the instructing authority, setting out what and what information should be supplied to him or generally as a guide to all authority who wish to instruct him to draft one law or the other.
- b. He can consult with the instructing office at an early stage after receipt of the preliminary drafting instructions. Drafting instructions are the instructions emanating from the authority sponsoring the law to the legislative draftsman who

6. Ibid 3

is responsible for reflecting policies in laws or statutes. The instructing authority could be anyone from the government. The legislative draftsman would; invariably, be a lawyer knowledgeable in the art of drafting laws and could be counsel or a legal practitioner commissioned to draft the law.

It is of great importance if the following are borne in mind and are contained in the drafting instruction:

- I. Sufficient background information to enable the draftsman to see in perspective and in context the facts and the problems which the legislative proposal is intended to meet.
- ii. The principal objects of the legislation must be clearly state.
- iii. The means whereby the principal objects are to be achieved should be stated.
- iv. All known implications, difficulties whether legal, social or administrative associated or contemplated by the proposals should be stated.

Apart from receiving the drafts instructions, it is advisable to meet with the officials of the sponsoring authority. Conference, formal and informal meetings may be appropriate to discern the mind of the instructing authority.

Analyzing the Draft

The draftsman should synthesize the instruction received such as whether there is an existing law, potential danger areas, and practicality of the policy and the categories of persons to whom the law is applicable. This analysis would help prevent a legislation that would eventually be pronounced a nullity by the courts. It also saves the time of the legislator in making or repeating existing legislation.

Designing the Draft

At this stage, the draftsman plan and design the structure of the draft Bill. After gaining thorough understanding of the proposals and assessing same in relation to existing law, the draftsman now reaches the design or planning stage. This is by outline the framework prepared by the draftsman that will assists him in visualizing the shape or broad content of the enactment.

The draftsman may be required to do the following:

- i. A precise outline of the objectives and principles to be contained in the legislation.

7. Ibid

8. Ibid

- ii. A statement of the principal means of attaining the objectives and principles.
- iii. Design the structure of the draft statute, e.g. the substantive provisions and the administration provisions of the bill.

Composing the draft

The draftsman will need the various aids for effective communication and skills in presenting the body of the Bill. For instance, Precedent books, existing laws, etc. composing a statute entails a lot of mental discipline. The draftsman will, invariably, rely on some aids to compose. These aids include precedents, statutes on similar subjects or related subjects, both local and other jurisdiction. Proper use of precedents may constitute a source of idea, in addition to constituting a help in the actual drafting. Use of precedents saves time and using precedents from the same jurisdiction may contribute in no small way to statute law, becoming a coherent body rather than a patch work.

Scrutinizing Stage

At this last stage of the draft, the draftsman should scrutinize and correct noticeable errors such as spellings, punctuations and possibly pass the draft to colleagues or superior for vetting. The draftsman should check and re-check the drafts in previous stages, and must have had series of conferences and meetings, both formal and informal, with those sponsoring the statute. Errors or mistakes, especially of substance and against the general intendments of the statute must have been detected and corrected. At this stage however, one should ask an independent eye, preferably a legal practitioner, to have another critical look at the draft, for someone who has been involved as the draftsman may not spot drafting and other clerical errors.

ARRANGEMENT OF DRAFTED LEGISLATION

It is important to arrange the legislative Bill into parts, segments and schedules for easy reference and understanding while reading the bill.

Divisions of Legislative Drafting

It is important to arrange a long statute in parts so as to make it clear in presentation and easy to read and follow, as far as reference goes. But length off statutes alone may not be the sole criterion for deciding whether it should be divided into parts. Division into parts may be necessary also, where running through the statue is the same. In some instances, there

9. Ibid

10. Ibid

may be differences in terms of specific provisions for administration and execution. For example, the statues may relate to mining with provision for its administration by a statutory body. Naturally, provisions would be made for the establishment of the statutory body and its powers for mining and mineral resources, etc. Whatever the case, the mining theme runs throughout these provisions.

Therefore, this is the reason why legislations are drafted in parts and forms for clarity and ease of reference.

1. **Parts:** legislations are usually divided into Parts for ease of reference. The parts are at times numbered in Roman Numerals e.g. Part i, ii, iii, etc.
2. **Marginal Notes:** This is also referred to as 'Statutory Signpost'. They are usually in the margin of the legislation.

Legislative Segments

A drafted legislation could be divided into four or five segments. This should not be mixed up with division into parts. "Segments" here means skeleton or design upon which the draftsman builds. Legislations are usually divided into the following segments;

- i. **Preliminary Provision** is made up of the Long Title, Preamble, Enacting clause, Short title, Application, Interpretation, Commencement and Duration.
- ii. **Principal provisions** which can either be substantive or administrative provision dealing with main issues in the Bill.
- iii. **Miscellaneous Provisions** e.g. Offences, penalties and supplementary provisions.
- iv. **Final provisions** such as savings, transitional provisions, repeals, consequential amendments.

Schedule

This is like an annexure to the bill with details which could neither be accommodated incorporated in the principal provisions.

LEGISLATIVE TERMINOLOGIES

Legislative terminologies includes the following:

Bill: It is a proposed law or proposal to the legislative houses such as Senate, House of Representatives and House of Assembly.

11 Ibid

12. Ibid

Types of Bills: There are basically two types of bills:

- a. **Executive Bill:** An Executive Bill is also known as Government Bill or public Bill is the kind of proposed law sponsored by the Government for Consideration and passage into Law. The bill can be from any of the Executive arm of Government either at the State level of Federal level of government. It is the kind of bill that affects or applies to every person or the whole country or state, or any part of it and the bill will premise on any subject the legislators has power to legislate upon. An example of Public Bill is Annual Budget,
- b. **Private Bill:** This is the type of bill sponsored by private member of the Parliament or Private institution or Non-Governmental Organisation or any outsider who is interested in the codification of such Law.

Act: This is a bill passed by the National Assembly.

Law: This is a bill passed by the States Houses of Assembly.

Rules/Order: These are usually made by an authority empowered to make rules to regulate an aspect under an Act/Law. For instance, the various heads of courts of law such as the Chief Justice of Nigeria enjoys the power to make rules of that court in line with statutory provisions. Most Chief Judges of states enjoy the power to make practice directions for the various courts under their jurisdiction.

Bye-Law: This is a Bill passed by the Local Government Councils and a times; it may be made by associations or pressure groups.

THE LEGISLATIVE CONCEPTS

A legal draftsman must be able to properly arrange the body of his legislation and bring out the following legislative concepts as explained below:

- a. **Long Title:** Under the procedures of Parliament in the United Kingdom, the long title is important since, a bill cannot be amended to go outside the scope of its long title. For that reason, modern long titles tend to be rather vague, ending with the formulation "and for connected purposes".

13. Ibid

14. Ibid

The wording after "An Act" varies somewhat between jurisdictions. In some jurisdictions, including the United Kingdom, the long title opens with the words "An Act to ..." For example, the short title of the House of Lords Act 1999 is "*House of Lords Act 1999*", but its long title is "*An Act to restrict membership of the House of Lords by virtue of a hereditary peerage; to make related provision about disqualifications for voting at elections to, and for membership of, the House of Commons; and for connected purposes.*" The United Kingdom Bills substitute the words "A Bill" for "An Act". Thus, before it passed the bill into law, the long title of the House of Lords Bill 1999 was "A Bill to restrict membership..." It is noted that many of the British long titles are quite long because of the way they are used to define the scope of bills.

The long title comes at the beginning of the law giving clues as to the intent of the law and possibly its direct interpretation as it is intended to provide a summarised description of the purpose or scope of the instrument. The long title is part of the statute, being considered, enacted, and subject to amendment, by the legislature. The long title seldom affects the operative provisions of an act, except where the operative provisions are unclear or ambiguous and the long title provides a clear statement of the legislature's intention. A comprehensive long title may serve a valuable purpose in assisting to communicate the intended spirit and scope of the statute. The long title should be drafted in terms wide enough to embrace the whole of the contents of a Bill. Where the law is to repeal or amend an existing law, the long title must state so. An example of a long title reads thus:

A BILL FOR AN ACT TO ENSURE FULL COMPLIANCE WITH THE ANTI-TERRORISM TREATY OF ROME, ESTABLISH THE ANTI-PIRACY COMMISSION FOR THE PURPOSES SET OUT IN THE TREATY AND OTHER MATTERS INCIDENTAL THEREOF.

or

AN ACT TO ESTABLISHED FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY OTUGBO TO ENABLE THE PEOPLE OF OTUGBO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY AND ENVIRONS TO HAVE EASY ACCESS TO TERTIARY EDUCATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN CAPACITY FOR NIGERIA.

- b. **Short Title:** While the long title, precedes the preamble and enacting formula, and thus sits outside the main body of text, the short title of a modern legislation is explicitly defined by a specific section, particularly at the beginning or at the end of the main text. Short titles are generally made up of just few words that describe in broad terms the area of law being changed or the thing affected, followed by the word "Act" and then the year that the legislation is enacted. In some cases, the word "Act" may be replaced with another descriptor like "Law" and "Charter."

In a few cases, some Acts particularly have more than one short title given to them, for example because subsequent amendments to their contents have rendered the earlier name inaccurate. Notwithstanding the repeal of an enactment giving a short title to an Act, the act may, without prejudice to any other mode of citation, continue to be cited by that short title.

The distinction between the long and short titles of an Act

In England, short titles for acts of Parliament were not introduced until the mid-19th century and were not provided for every act passed until late in the century. Instead, the long title was used to identify the Act. Short titles were subsequently given to many Acts that remained un-repealed. For instance, the Bill of Rights of 1689 was initially referred to only by its long title. It was later that short title was given to the Act by the Short Titles Act of 1896. For instance, while the example of a long title will be "*An Act Declaring the Rights and Liberties of the Subject and Settling the Succession of the Crown*", the short title of the same Act will be "*Rights and Liberties Act, 2016*"

Where there are laws that relate primarily to other laws, such as amendments, the short title of the former will be quoted in the latter law. For example, the Sustainable Communities Act 2007 (Amendment) Act 2010. Subsequent enactments can lead to particularly lengthy short titles; for example, the Artizans' and Labourers' Dwellings Act 1868, amended by the Artizans' and Labourers' Dwellings Act 1868 (Amendment) Act 1869, and itself amended by the Artizans' and Labourers' Dwellings Act 1868 (Amendment) Act 1879 (Amendment) Act 1880.

16. Tanner George, *Imperatives in drafting legislation a brief New Zealand perspective*,. *Commonwealth Law Bulletin*. (Sixth ed), 2005.

17. *Halsbury's Laws of England*. Fourth Edition. Reissue. 1995. Volume 44(1). *Statutes* para. 1253, 1268.

18 Tobias A Dorsey. *Legislative Drafter's Deskbook: A Practical Guide*. The Capitol.Net Inc. Pages 224 to 227, 2006.
19 Section 3, The Short Titles Act 1896, (Ireland).

In the case of *Marbury v. Madison*, Supreme Court of the United States of America, first declared Judiciary Act of 1789, an act of Congress unconstitutional based on an inconsistent title.

If a law is passed with the same title as another law passed in the same year, an ordinal number will be added to distinguish it from the others. This is particularly common for Finance Acts e.g. Finance (No. 3) Act 2010 and commencement orders that bring parts of an Act into force e.g. Environment (Commencement No.13) Act 1995.

- c. **Preamble:** It is included as an opening statement and simply states the reasons why the law becomes desirable. It is rarely used in modern legislative drafting except in certain circumstances such as constitutions of Nations, International treaties, Conventions of Nations, International treaties, Conventions and Protocols. Like the long title, a preamble is part of a statute and may be used as an aid to construction. The main function of a preamble is to explain the object of the legislation or to explain the reasons why its enactment is considered desirable. A preamble should be provided if it will serve a demonstrably useful purpose in the particular circumstances. An example is the preamble to the 1999 constitution of the federal republic of Nigerian as follows:

We the people of the federal republic of Nigeria having firmly and solemnly resolve, to live in unity and harmony as one indivisible and indissoluble sovereign nation under God, dedicated to the promotion of inter-African solidarity, world peace, international co-operation and understanding. And to provide for a constitution for the purpose of promoting the good government and welfare of all persons in our country, on the principles of freedom, equality and justice, and for the purpose of consolidating the unity of our people
Do hereby make, enact and give to ourselves the following constitution:-

- d. **Commencement:** The commencement of the legislation enables us to know when such legislation comes into force or becomes operative. It enables the drafter to know the various ways commencement of legislation can be determined. An example of the commencement clause is the writing of the date at the right hand side of the legislation immediately after the long title e.g., a statute may come into

20 Maclaurin, H. N. (11 September 1893). Sanitary Legislation and Administration in England. Votes & Proceedings. Vol. 2. New South Wales Legislative Council. p. 44. 1893

21 5 U.S. (1 Cranch) 137 (1803)

force on the date the Chief Executive of the executive arm of government assents to it. For instance, this act shall come into force on the date the president gives his assent.

Commencement provisions are best presented in one separate section or subsection where they can be easily found. There are four possibilities:

- i. The legislation may make no specific provision,
- ii. It may specify a date for the commencement,
- iii. It may empower some person or persons to specify a commencement data; and
- iv. It may provide for the legislation to commence upon the occurrence of a stipulated event.

The general rule applicable in default may provide for commencement on the day of assent or on the day of publication in the Gazette.

This act come into force in day as the Minister of Justice appoints by Notice in the Gazette.

This Act comes into force on the same day as the money Laundering (prohibition) Act 2017 comes into force

FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA as follow:

Or

THE NATIONAL ASSEMBLY OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA ENACTS as follows:

- e. **Enacting Formula:** This clause usually acquaint us with the enacting which differs from jurisdiction to jurisdiction, e.g. Federal government (the whole federation) Laws made by the National Assembly. For instance, ENACTED BY THE NATIONAL ASSEMBLY OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA.

- f. **Establishment clause:** This establishes the administering or statutory body to the law, states their powers and duties. Where the law does not set up an administering body to the enactment, there is no need for an establishment clause. See *ACME Builders v. KSEB*. It is drafted thus:

There shall be established a body to be known as the national commission for museums and monuments.

Or

There is hereby established a body to be known as the national commission for museums and monuments.

- g. Short Title/Citation:** The short title clause identifies, describes, and cites the statute. Lord Mouton in *Vacher & Sons Ltd v London Society* described short title as a statutory nickname to obviate the necessity of always referring to the Act under its full and descriptive title. The short title has the characteristics of a label. While a long title need not be long, but a short title must necessarily be short. The short title should not be enclosed in inverted commas. An example is drafted thus:

This Act may be cited as the Companies and Allied Matters Act Cap C59 LFN 2004

Or where it is amendment legislation, it may be drafted thus:

This Act may be cited as the Federal University of Technology, Otuogbe (Establishment) Act 2022.

- h. Application:** The application of a law could be all encompassing or specific, It could be territorial or limited to specific things e.g. the NDLEA Act of the legislation may serve to remove to uncertainties and solve problems as to the manner in which a new statute is to affect the variety of complete situation and transactions existing at the moment in time when that law comes into force.

Application provision may concern the application of the legislation to any of the following:

The circumstance existing when the legislation comes into force

The territorial area

Specific persons or things

The Federal, State or Local Government

For example, it may be drafted thus:

Part 2 and section 17 apply to Federal capital Territory only.

Or

This act applies to every civil proceeding commenced after this Act comes into force

- i. Duration:** Generally, a legislative proposal once passed into law is in perpetuity. It continues to be in force until it is repealed. This clause states the lifespan of an enactment, and it is applicable in instances where the duration or the purpose for

22 (1999) 2NWLR (pt590) 288@ 313

23 (1913) AC 107 @128

which the law is made is specific as it was held in the case of *Ibidapo v. Lufthansa Airlines*. For instance;

This Act shall continue to be in force until the 31st day of July 2011. And shall then cease to have the force of law unless otherwise stated by the house through the enactment of another legislation which determines otherwise.

or

This Act comes into force on 23rd 2016 and continues to be in force for 4 years after that date.

- j. **Savings:** This is used to preserve or save a law, a right or a privilege which would otherwise be repealed or ceased to have effect. E.g. *Save and except otherwise stated, section 17 of this act shall not be replaced under this amendment.*
- k. **Repeals:** This clause terminates the operative force of a particular legislation. This may be stated expressly or by implication. See *Re Raleigh industries (Nig) Ltd*. See also the effect of the repeal of a law in the case of **Sossa v Fokpo**.
- l. **Schedule:** This is a device in a law which banishes the detail or matter of technical nature in the enactment to the latter end of the enactment. This is to avoid clumsiness and distraction and distraction in the body or core parts of the legislation when reading it. *A.G. v Lamplough, Egolum v. Obasanjo*.
- m. **Explanatory notes:** This does not really form part of a law but explains generally the purpose of the law. See examples in treaties and constitution of nation
- n. **Definition or Interpretation Section:** This gives meaning and explains the intent of the word used in the legislation. It can be restrictive e.g. includes

It may also be drafted thus:

*Lecturer includes: Research Assistant, Assistant Lecturer,
Vice – Chancellor Means: Vice – Chancellor of a university.*

LAW MAKING PROCESS

This is the procedure of passing the bill drafted into Law.

24 (1997) 4 NWLR pt498 124.

Law Making Process in National Assembly or State House of Assembly

The stages a bill goes through before becoming an Act or Statute can be divided as follows:

- 1st stage ----- Introduction of the bill or drafted law
- 2nd Stage ----- First Reading
- 3rd Stage ----- Second Reading
- 4th Stage ----- Committee Stage
- 5th Stage ----- Report Stage
- 6th Stage ----- Third Reading (Consideration of the Amendments)
- 7th Stage ----- Production of Clean Copy
- 8th Stage ----- Assent by the Governor or the President.

CONCLUSION

Having the requisite skills as professional drafter, the following will be taken into account before the commencement of the drafting of the Bill;

Analysis of the Instruction received to know the practicality of the intention in line with existing Law before moving to the next step.

Planning and Designing the drafting process by visualizing the shape or broad content of the enactment.

Research and composing the body of the Bill by invariably relying on some aids to be used. These aids include precedents, statutes on similar subjects or related subjects, both local and other jurisdictions. Proper use of precedents may constitute a source of idea, in addition to constituting a help in the actual drafting.

Scrutinizing the draft by checking for noticeable errors and consulting another person who is skillful in legislative drafting to go through for any clerical Error.

25 (1994) 4 NWLR (pt342) 760.

26 (2000) FWLR (pt 22)1111.

27 (1878) EXCH. DIV. 214

28 (1999) 5 SCNJ 71 @129

29 *Ese Malemi: The Nigerian Constitutional Law.* pg 206-207

LEGISLATIVE DRAFTING CHART

References

1. Prof. Epiphany Azinge; *Fundamentals of Legislative Drafting*. Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies 2012
2. Prof, Matti Niemivuo: "Legislative Drafting Process. Main Issues And Some Examples"; European Commission For Democracy Through Law (Venice Commission)
3. Prof. O.B. Akinola: *Principles of Law in Practice (Professional Ethics & skills)*
4. Ese Malemi: *The Nigeria Constitutional Law* pg 204-205
5. Tanner George, *Imperatives in drafting legislation a brief New Zealand perspective*,. *Commonwealth Law Bulletin*. (Sixth ed), 2005.
6. *Halsbury's Laws of England*. Fourth Edition. Reissue. 1995. Volume 44(1). *Statutes* para. 1253, 1268.
7. Tobias A Dorsey. *Legislative Drafter's Deskbook: A Practical Guide*. The Capitol.Net Inc. Pages 224 to 227, 2006.
8. Maclaurin, H. N. (11 September 1893). *Sanitary Legislation and Administration in England*. *Votes & Proceedings*. Vol. 2. New South Wales Legislative Council. p. 44. 1893

9. *Marbury v. Madison* 5 U.S. (1 Cranch) 137 (1803)
10. *ACME Builders v. KSEB* (1999) 2NWLR (pt590) 288@ 313
11. *Vacher & Sons Ltd v London Society* (1913) AC 107 @128
12. *Ibidapo v. Lufthansa Airlines* (1997) 4 NWLR pt498 124.
13. *Re Raleigh industries (Nig) Ltd* (1994) 4 NWLR (pt342) 760.
14. *Sossa v Fokpo* (2000) FWLR (pt 22)1111.
15. *A.G. v Lamplough* (1878) EXCH. DIV. 214
16. *Egolum v. Obasanjo* (1999) 5 SCNJ 71 @129
17. *Ese Malemi: The Nigerian Constitutional Law.* pg 206-207